
Hydrogels are promising considering their incredible capacity to modify, encapsulate and co-deliver medicinal compounds, cells, biomolecules, and nanomaterials

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Abstract: As many medications are administered jointly, they often give larger benefits, counteract disadvantages, and enhance treatment results compared to monotherapy. Whether natural or synthetic, injectable biomaterials can form degradable networks in situ, decreasing patient pain and cost while presenting new and promising possibilities for minimally invasive surgery. Biomaterials' ability to create and manufacture injectable systems is strongly impacted by their physicochemical and mechanical properties. The design and manufacture of injectable systems containing cells, therapeutic molecules, particles, and biomolecules that can be injected into geometrically complex body tissue regions poses a significant challenge as they must ensure drug/biomolecule/material bioactivity, cell survival and retention. Hydrogels are a promising choice in this case given their amazing ability to manipulate, encapsulate and co-deliver pharmaceutical chemicals, cells, biomolecules, and nanomaterials. Hydrogels can alter their mechanical and deteriorating qualities by adjusting the cross-linking technique and chemical composition. The ability to modify IH's mechanical strength permits co-encapsulation of medicinal compounds, cells, nanomaterials, and growth factors in the matrix in situ, allowing for multimodal synergistic therapies.

To boost the prospects of translating IHs into normal clinics, various barriers and outstanding scientific issues must be tackled in the future. Future investigations, including the application of IHs in multimodal synergistic treatment, should start with large animal models such as monkeys and dogs or even ex vivo human tissue models. In addition, the period of in vivo evaluations should be prolonged from weeks to months for trustworthy and accurate data to be translated to clinical trials. On the one hand, the toxicity of certain crosslinking agents used in IH synthesis must be considered, as the residues will cause unwanted in vivo reactions. Toxic crosslinkers, on the other hand, may interact with therapeutic molecules/biomolecules or nanomaterials trapped in the hydrogel matrix, causing loss of bioactivity. Similarly, IHs' sol-gel transition is a vital issue requiring much investigation. A quick sol-gel transition of precursor solutions might cause the fluid to be caught in the needle, whereas high-viscosity precursor solutions need high injection force, resulting in physician hand fatigue and patient annoyance. Other concerns for clinical IH translation include fast release and rate of degradation. Degradation rate is critical in controlling therapeutic drug release and tissue regeneration. Fast hydrogel breakdown may trigger early inflammatory reaction due to breakdown products, whereas delayed degradation may result in insufficient release of therapeutic drugs. Changing the composition, structure, and crystallinity of polymers must be employed to customize the breakdown rate. Expert researchers will be better equipped to tackle these challenges if they have a deeper knowledge of polymers' physiochemical features. Overall, future IH design should focus on building simple, well-defined 3D networks with low toxicity, high biodegradation rate, and acceptable functionality.

1. Introduction

Changes in lifestyle, nutrition, physiological, and environmental conditions have resulted in an increase in difficult-to-treat diseases and socioeconomic challenges around the world, including cancer, cardiovascular disorders, neurodegenerative disorders, and infectious diseases, all of which pose a death threat to humans. (1) and (2) Due to the physiological complexity of hard-to-treat illnesses, clinical experience and exploratory investigations have proven in the last decade that a single therapy method may be unable to adequately combat them. (3) As a result, recent discoveries have gradually drifted away from monotherapy and toward combination or multiple treatments, because the synergy of therapeutic substances or procedures produces substantial superadditive (that is, " $1 + 1 > 2$ ") therapeutic benefits. (4) As a result, combining or multiple treatments have been advocated as an alternative to monotherapy to address the drawbacks. (5) Despite their many benefits, existing combinations or multiple treatments have a number of limitations that may restrict their usage in clinical practice. Some medications' potentiation for combined or multiple therapy, for example, is extremely sequence dependent, and hence their simultaneous combination fails to provide synergistic benefits against difficult-to-treat disorders. (6) Furthermore, the difficulties of formulation development have slowed the growth of multi-therapeutics. For example, the Gliadel wafer, a post-surgical drug delivery implant designed to prevent tumor recurrence, (7) has several drawbacks, including rapid drug release, inability to adapt to the shape and anatomy of the desired site, and subsequent implant dislodgement, high rigidity of the structure, and thus the need for a large resection cavity size (especially for the treatment of glioblastoma). (8) As a result, new platforms should be devised to allow for the simultaneous loading of several therapeutic molecules into implants, for example, to produce antibacterial and anti-inflammatory characteristics while killing cancer cells following surgical excision of cancer tissue. (9) New injectable platforms with adhesion qualities and the potential to allow smart and sustained release of therapeutic compounds are urgently needed in this area. (9) The proper integration of numerous therapeutic molecules in a single platform, rather than simple mixing, is critical for the realization, specificity, and durability of combination or multiple treatments to achieve positive synergistic effects. (9) Rapid breakthroughs in nanotechnology and biomaterials have made it possible to assemble a platform from a variety of medications, growth factors, and particles via chemical interactions or simple physical adsorption without losing bioactivity. (12) Hydrogels are three-dimensional networks of cross-linked polymer chains that can absorb large volumes of water and biological fluids and can be used as controlled drug delivery platforms or as an artificial extracellular matrix (ECM) for tissue engineering. (13) Furthermore, certain polymeric hydrogel systems feature shear thinning and self-recovery capabilities, or can be produced in situ within the body after being injected as a liquid. (14) These properties allow for the creation of injectable hydrogels (IHs) (15, 16) that are promising candidates for cancer therapy, cartilage repair, angiogenesis and vascularization, (19-21) tissue engineering, (22) nervous system repair, (19) therapeutic delivery, (23, 24) wound healing, (25, 26) and other applications. Physical contacts (ionic and hydrophobic contacts, as well as supramolecular chemistry), non-toxic chemical crosslinkers, or biological cross-linking by enzymes can all be used to create in situ forming hydrogels. (27)

IHs are ideal candidates for biomedical applications because of their outstanding properties, such as ease of handling and use, minimal invasiveness, the ability for simple and long-term cell and growth factor encapsulation without chemical cross-linking, shape adaptability,

proper adherence to the surrounding tissues during in situ formation, and improved patient compliance. 16, 28

The idea of modifying and optimizing IHs for various therapies is still in its infancy. The unusual structure of IHs allows for the effective trapping of large payloads of various therapeutic agents, as well as their protection against enzymatic degradation and regulated release in the target region. 11 and 29 We explore methods for fabricating and characterisation of IHs, as well as recent breakthroughs in their use for multitherapy of cancer, wound healing, and other disorders, in this review.

2 IH Preparation Procedures Chemical or physical cross-linking methods can be used to make IHs in general. Physical cross-linking can be achieved by secondary forces, in which non-covalent interactions lead to the development of polymeric networks without the need for chemical stimuli. The physically cross-linked IHs were designed using non-covalent interactions such as hydrophobic interactions, hydrogen bonding, ion cross-linking, and host-guest interactions. Although physically cross-linked IHs are biocompatible and have low cytotoxicity for human health, they often have mechanically unstable properties due to transient junctions between the chains. Chemically cross-linked IHs, on the other hand, are made by forming new covalent connections between polymer chains, resulting in permanent and stable junctions with excellent mechanical characteristics.

However, possible hazardous compounds used in the creation of this type of hydrogel, such as cross-linking monomers, photo-initiators, organic solvents, or catalysts, may limit their in vivo use. (number 30) Chemical cross-linking has been done in a variety of ways, according to the literature. (31) These technologies produce hydrogels with good mechanical capabilities, which can be used to create IHs with long-lasting characteristics. (32) Overall, traditional cross-linking procedures may not be specialized enough to produce injectable gels, but they are enough for the production of regular hydrogels. The gelling kinetics can have a big influence on bulk gel molding and injectability/mass transfer.

2.1 Physical Cross-Linking Techniques

2.1.1 Hydrogels with Ionic Cross-Linking

Mixing ionizable polymers with counter-ions results in ionic cross-linked hydrogels. Changes in ion concentrations, gelator concentrations, and electrical density, pH, and temperature can all affect the injectability of these hydrogels. Similarly, the cross-linking density and molecular weight of the polymers can alter the structure's mechanical strength. Due to the significant quantity of carboxyl groups in their structure, certain macromolecules, such as alginate, can be cross-linked by adding cationic donors, such as calcium chloride. Combining oppositely charged polyelectrolytes, such as sodium alginate, polylysine, and hyaluronic acid, is another way to make an ionic cross-linking hydrogel (HA). (33) The strong interaction of two oppositely charged polyelectrolytes and, as a result, the production of an inhomogeneous mixture with big aggregates is a key drawback of this method. (34) Wu et al. employed a static mixing technique to generate polyelectrolyte complex (PEC) IHs containing polyglutamate and chitosan to resolve this problem (CS). (34) This same team used a moderate gelation approach to add spherical hydroxyapatite to PEC IHs and discovered that it had a high capacity for injection with a 27G needle and improved soft tissue regeneration. (35)

2.1.2 Hydrophobic Interactions

Amphiphilic polymers' hydrophobic moieties can mediate hydrogel formation through physical interactions.(36) Several approaches, such as block or random copolymerizations, and the decorating of hydrophilic macromolecules with pendant hydrophobic moieties, can be used to make amphiphilic polymers. '37' Polymeric amphiphiles having an upper critical solution temperature (UCST) or a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) may be suitable alternatives for injectability since a change in ambient temperature causes a sol–gel transition and then hydrogel formation. '37' Because the gelation condition of such polymers is temperature dependent, it is important to choose a critical temperature that is near to the body's environment. (38)

2.1.3 – Interaction with Stacking

The interaction between relatively-electron-rich groups and-electron-deficient groups of aromatic compounds can produce – stacking bonds. Based on the geometry of aromatic interactions, the – stacking interaction may be divided into three types: I stacked face-to-surface, ii stacked edge-to-face (T-shaped), and iii stacked offset.(40) Two kinds of – stacking interactions in hydrogels have been reported: plane-to-plane and edge-to-plane. (40) Amino acids like tyrosine, tryptophan, and phenylalanine may be suitable options for facilitating – stacking in hydrogels because of their water-rich composition. As a result, employing gelling materials with pre-designed peptides can guarantee the creation of IHs through the – stacking interaction. (41)

2.1.4 Hydrogen Bonding

Hydrogen bonding has been suggested as a viable cross-linking technique since it allows for the simultaneous synthesis of IHs with thermoplasticity and self-healing characteristics. Hydrogen bonding, on the other hand, is dynamic in nature, and it breaks at high temperatures. (42) The limited stability of hydrogen bonding cross-linked hydrogels in water, which is owing to hydration and hydrogen bonding segregation between polymer segments, is a key drawback that may restrict their use in biological applications. Several strategies have been proposed to overcome this issue and improve the mechanical characteristics of hydrogen bonding cross-linked hydrogels. Using macromolecules with two amide moieties (forming dual hydrogen bonding structures) or nanoclays as bioink for changing structural viscosity are two examples. (42-44). Several functional moieties, such as 2-ureido-4-(1H)-pyrimidinone (UPy), diaminotriazine (DAT), and 6-aminocaproic acid (6-ACA), can be used to create hydrogen (H) bond-based hydrogels with distinct stimuli responsiveness and shear thinning capabilities.(43, 45)

UPy is one of the most promising functional moieties for the preparation of H-bonding cross-linked IHs.(45) With triple H-bonds, this moiety can form a UPy–UPy dimer. Changes in pH and temperature can be used to modulate the sol–gel transition of IHs thanks to the remarkable characteristics of UPy. (45, 46) Another functional moiety, 6-ACA, can be employed to make H-bond cross-linked IHs with reversible self-healing capacity in response to pH-induced damage. The H-bonds between the amide and carboxylic acid moieties of two sections of hydrogels cause self-healing. IHs generated by 6-ACA have high self-healing capacity and great adherence to new gastric mucosa, making them effective platforms for prolonged release of medicinal compounds in a low pH environment or ideal tissue adhesives for stomach perforations. (47)

2.1.5 Interaction between the host and the guest

Another physical cross-linking technique is host–guest chemistry, in which typical host molecules such as crown ethers, cyclodextrins, and cucurbiturils are grafted onto polymer backbones as pendent or end moieties. (48) The host–guest chemistry has various benefits, including reversibility, the capture of therapeutic molecules by the host moieties, and the avoidance of burst release, making it an appealing cross-linking technique for creating IHs for drug delivery and tissue engineering. (49, 50) IHs formed by host–guest interactions, on the other hand, undergo mild gelation processing without the use of cross-linking agents or the generation of heat during polymerization, which can obstruct the denaturation of incorporated proteins and cause damage to encapsulated cells at the gelation site. (Fifty)

2.2 Cross-Linking Strategies Using Chemicals

2.2.1 Chemistry (Click)

One of the chemical cross-linking techniques with relatively fast kinetics is click chemistry. The click chemistry technique has several features that make it a promising choice for the creation of IHs, including biocompatibility, selectivity, adaptability, spontaneous reactions, fast reaction rates, high product yields, and high capacity for in situ gel formation. (51)

To make hydrogels, researchers employed a variety of click chemistry techniques, including non-alkyl carbonyl chemistry, nucleophilic ring-opening reaction, thiol–ene addition, azide–nitrile addition, carboncarbon multi-bond addition reaction, and cycloaddition reaction.(52) The requirement for the presence of an initiator and/or a catalyst for the reaction, which might obstruct its bioactive use, is a key barrier for this method. Attempts to use non-catalyst/initiator reactions for the manufacture of ecologically acceptable IHs are now being made in large numbers. (53) The ability to generate strong high water content (90 percent) hydrogels with variable mechanical and stiffness characteristics is a significant benefit of click chemistry. (54)

2.2.2 Cross-Linking of Photographs

Photo cross-linking is a chemical cross-linking strategy for preparing IHs in which electromagnetic light in the UV and visible ranges is used to induce cross-linking by activating photo-initiators and producing cations or free radicals.(55) a Initiation (excitation of photoinitiators and development of free radicals), propagation (interaction with photocurable macromers and synthesis of reactive species), and termination are the three processes in this technique (the end of cross-linking and formation of 3D structure). (56) The advantages of photo-crosslinked hydrogels include good viability of encapsulated cells due to moderate gelation conditions and fine temporal and spatial control over the gelation process. (57)

Photoinitiation may be divided into numerous categories based on the polymerization reaction, such as cationic polymerization, radical photopolymerization by hydrogen abstraction, and radical photopolymerization by photocleavage. A key downside of this method has been suggested to be the poor rate of light penetration in the gelling mixture. (58) Many research organizations have employed visible light instead of UV light since it has a better penetration rate and causes less tissue damage. (59)

2.2.3.3 Addition Reaction of the Michael Type

Under physiological conditions, the Michael addition reaction is based on the addition of a nucleophile (electron donor) such as amine or thiols to unsaturated carbonyl molecules such as aldehydes and ketones (electron receptor).(60) The fraction of electron donor or electron

receptor, the concentration of polymer solution, and its molecular weight all have a significant impact on the gelling period of IHs.

(number 60) Due to the requirement for a high temperature and alkaline environment, Michael's addition to amines is not suited for in situ creation of IHs. Because the reaction happens spontaneously under physiological circumstances, Michael addition with thiols is a viable candidate for producing in situ IHs. (61) (61) (61) Li et al. synthesized thiol derivatized hyaluronan (HA-SH) as an electron acceptor and maleilated collagen (Col-MA) as an electron donor, and discovered that injecting them into the target region resulted in fast hydrogel production (rapid gelation time of about 40 s). (62) Although acrylates are the most often employed electrophiles for Michael additions, vinyl sulfones and maleimides have been shown to have greater cross-linking rates. (60, 63) If you're looking for a unique way to express yourself, Hubbell et al. designed and fabricated several types of in situ forming hydrogels based on Michael addition that are appealing for biomedical applications because they have low toxicity due to rapid formation under physiological conditions without the use of a catalyst and the absence of any byproducts. (64)

2.2.4 Schiff Base Cross-Linking

The interaction of amine and aldehyde moieties provides the basis for Schiff base cross-linking.(65) It's also worth mentioning that the quantity of amines and aldehyde moieties used in this method determines the gelation duration and intensity of the IHs produced. (57) Schiff base linkages, such as oximes, imines, and hydrazones, are formed through condensation reactions between aldehyde and amine moieties. (66) (66) (66) Biocompatibility, reversibility, pH sensitivity, and simplicity are all features of the Schiff base cross-linking, making it a good contender for designing smart hydrogels for biomedical purposes. (26, 19) One of the drawbacks of employing Schiff base cross-linking to make IHs is that free aldehyde moieties in the polymer's backbone might react with amine moieties in biomolecules, resulting in toxicity and other side effects. (18, 67)

2.2.5 Enzymatic Reaction

Enzymatic cross-linking is a chemical cross-linking strategy that uses a variety of enzymes (such as transglutaminases, phosphatases, glucose oxidase (GOx), tyrosinase, laccase, and horseradish peroxidase (HRP)) extracted from animal and plant sources to facilitate the formation of protein-based IHs. (68) Transglutaminases, (69, 70), tyrosinases, (71), and peroxidases are the most often utilized enzymes in the preparation of IHs. (72) Transglutaminases are thiol enzymes that help build a covalent link between the α -carboxamide moieties of peptide-bound glutamine and free amine moieties of other macromolecules. Tyrosinases are copper-containing enzymes that help to produce activated quinones by oxidizing phenols in the presence of oxygen. The creation of a macromolecular network is then caused by the interaction of activated quinones with amino or hydroxyl moieties through a Michael-type addition reaction. Another class of enzymes that primarily employ H₂O₂ as a substrate is peroxidases. HRP is a peroxidase that enables the conjugation of phenol and aniline derivatives in the presence of H₂O₂ and is the most often utilized peroxidase in the synthesis of IHs. (73)

The use of an enzymatic process to make IHs is a dependable approach with various benefits, including reaction under physiological settings, high crosslinking efficiency, and biocompatibility. The enzyme concentration is a key element in the gelation duration and

hydrogel breakdown rate in this approach. (69) 3 IHs are used to treat cancer in a variety of ways.

Despite recent improvements in the development of innovative treatment techniques, cancer patients' survival rates remain dismal. (74) Multiple treatments using one or more therapeutic agents or distinct processes may be a preferable choice due to the diversity, complexity, and heterogeneity of malignancies, as well as the high costs of cancer drug development. (75) When compared to monotherapy, this method can improve treatment efficacy and minimize medication resistance by addressing the pathogenesis route in a synergistic manner. (76) The following section discusses recent breakthroughs in IH-based multimodal synergistic treatment for cancer metastasis and multidrug resistance.

3.1 IHs for the Co-Delivery of Cancer-Fighting Therapeutics

Controlled co-delivery of anticancer medications is an effective cancer treatment strategy in which IHs can play an important role as a smart drug carrier. The majority of research in this field has focused on achieving synergistic therapeutic effects through the effective combination of medicines and IH systems. In addition to their ability to transport therapeutic compounds in tandem, IHs are frequently able to transport medications and genes at the same time to combat tumor development and metastasis. Liu et al. (77) produced a peritumoral IH containing-cyclodextrin (-CD) and a positively charged amphiphilic copolymer) methoxy-poly (ethylene glycol)-b-poly (-caprolactone)-b-poly (ethylene imine) (targeted for folic acid (FA)) (named as MPEG-PCL-PEI-FA). In this study, researchers used a combination of paclitaxel (PTX) and the Nur77 B-cell lymphoma-2 (Bcl-2) conversion gene to limit the development of Bcl-2 overexpressed therapeutic-resistant malignancies in a targeted way. The PTX was loaded into the carrier's hydrophobic part, while Nur77 was adsorbed into the cationic region via electronic interactions. The results showed that a peritumoral injection of MPEG-PCL-PEI/-CD supramolecular hydrogel suppressed tumor development in a sustained way (for seven days), owing to IH's sluggish biodegradation. More intriguingly, the MPEG-PCL-PEI-FA/-CD supramolecular hydrogel with simultaneous Nur77 gene and PTX drug administration via controllable drug and plasmid deoxyribonucleic acid (pDNA) release and targeting ability mediated by FA ligand could outstandingly inhibit in vivo expression of Bcl-2 protein overexpressed in drug-resistant liver and lung cancer cells as well as subcut the expression of Bcl-2 protein overexpressed in drug (much better performance than the mere PTX loaded IH). (77)

The sustained release of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic therapeutic compounds from a delivery platform is a key difficulty linked with and applied to biomaterials for cancer treatment. This constraint has prompted researchers to create novel delivery methods, such as in situ IHs, that can be used to transport both hydrophilic and hydrophobic medicinal compounds with different chemical and physical characteristics for extended periods of time. Shen et al., for example, devised and manufactured a thermosensitive hydrogel that could transport both hydrophilic cisplatin and hydrophobic paclitaxel (PTX). They created the Bi (mPEG-PLGA) Pt (IV) (PtGel) by joining the hydrophobic ends of two mPEG-PLGA copolymers on the Pt (IV) as a cisplatin prodrug, which could generate an aqueous solution with a thermosensitive sol-to-gel transition characteristic. Furthermore, the core-corona micelles formed in the water as a result of the self-assembly of the amphiphilic cisplatin-polymer conjugates functioned as a reservoir for the PTX to be dissolved. As a result, an IH containing two medicines was created. Surprisingly, the PTX not only had anticancer properties, but it also lowered the IH's sol-gel transition temperature and boosted gel strength.

In vitro investigations revealed that these medications could be delivered in a controlled manner over a 2.5-month period, resulting in a synergistic anticancer impact on ovarian cancer cells. (78) They also claimed that injecting a hydrogel containing the two medication cocktails into an SKOV-3 ovarian cancer xenograft mice model resulted in a much lower tumor weight after four weeks than either treatment alone.

Furthermore, He et al. (79) designed an IH to administer three medications, including sorafenib (SFN), doxorubicin (DOX), and metformin (MET), to cancer patients at the same time by distinct methods. To do this, a thiolated HA derivative was used to make the self-crosslinking IH (HA-SH). In vitro tests on this triple drug-loaded IH revealed that it was cytotoxic to breast cancer cells (4T-1, MCF-7, and MDA-MB-231 cells), and that the synergistic effects of the medications resulted in a higher rate of tumor cell death than single drug-loaded IH. Furthermore, an ex vivo histological analysis of the main organs of Balb/c mice revealed that this triple drug-loaded IH (Gel+DOX/SFN/MET) has less cytotoxicity than PBS, Gel, free drug-treated groups, Gel+DOX, and Gel+DOX/SFN groups, with only minor lesions visible in the Gel+DOX/SFN/MET treated groups' kidneys. Furthermore, due to the synergistic effects of these medications, the Gel+DOX/SFN/MET treated group was able to inhibit tumor metastasis. (79) Yavvari et al. (80) created CS-catechol (CS-CAT)-based drug-loaded IH (CAT-Gel) to treat murine lung and breast cancer models using catechol-Fe (III) coordinative cross-linking. This self-healing injectable polymeric drug carrier had very minimal hemolytic and cytotoxic effects. The amphipathic structure of the polymer allowed them to easily load hydrophilic DOX hydrochloride and hydrophobic docetaxel (DTX) into the IH. Separately, the gel may load DOX at a rate of 2.5 wt% and DTX at a rate of 25 wt%. When it came to co-loading, 2.5 wt% DOX and 12.5 wt% DTX were utilized since the larger quantity had a detrimental influence on the gel-forming ability. The rheology studies confirmed the material's ability to self-heal. The regulated release of the encapsulated anticancer medications DOX and DTX via synergistic effects increased the median survival against the mouse lung and breast cancer models after subcutaneous injection of the drug-loaded CAT-Gel into mice. Similarly, bioluminescence pictures revealed a substantial reduction in tumor development in DOX-DTX-Gel-treated animals compared to the control group. This approach may be able to successfully develop a novel IH for localized medication delivery and combination effects in cancer therapy. (80)

Xie et al. (81) created a CS-based IH that was cross-linked with telechelic difunctional poly (ethylene glycol) (DF-PEG-DF) and loaded with DOX, DTX, and iron oxide for stimuli-responsive drug release via magnetic nanoparticle-induced hyperthermia. The use of a dual-drug-loaded magnetic hydrogel in combination with heat resulted in excellent results in treating triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) cells and a considerable reduction in tumor size. The magnetic field was able to control the release of anticancer medications, resulting in combination chemotherapy and thermotherapy therapy. In vivo studies showed that drug co-delivery had a greater therapeutic impact and resulted in a smaller tumor size decrease than single drug-loaded IH. (81) Using a coaxial electrohydrodynamic atomization process, Davoodi et al. (2) produced poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA 50:50) and poly (D, L-lactic acid) core-shell polymeric microparticles containing cisplatin and PTX. They then implanted them in an antibacterial IH made of alginate-aldehyde and branched polyethyleneimine (PEI-25k) produced using Schiff's base reaction for local delivery of anticancer medicines to fight TNBC. As a result, the MDA-MB-231 cell line experienced a regulated release for 45 days and a synergistic impact, with three mechanisms dominating: denaturation of DNA strands, stability of microtubules, and formation of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS).

Embedding microparticles into this IH increased medication sustained release and reduced initial burst release, particularly in the case of cisplatin, and lowered cisplatin's significant toxicity in human patients. Furthermore, the IH proved to be a promising technique and a non-invasive method for keeping particles within the tumor cavity. Furthermore, when compared to free-drug treatment groups, microparticles/hydrogel formulations loaded with anti-cancer agents showed better therapeutic outcomes against aggressive tumor cells with synergistic anti-cancer activity against TNBC, indicating the high potential of IHs for multimodal synergistic therapy against cancers. (2)

3.2 IHs for Cancer Combination Therapy

In the last decade, radiation, chemotherapy, and high-intensity focused ultrasound treatment have all demonstrated substantial clinical effectiveness in terms of tumor growth reduction and patient survival. Other therapeutic possibilities, such as immunotherapy, photothermal therapy, magnetic hyperthermia, and gene therapy, are still in the early stages of clinical trials, but numerous preclinical papers have shown their high efficacy, which bodes well for future clinical translation. Nonetheless, single therapy approaches have been documented to fail to successfully slow tumor development. This section discusses cancer multitherapies involving IHs and the therapeutic alternatives described above.

Biom mineralization stimulated self-assembly of collagen protein by combining it with chloroauric acid (HAuCl₄) in acid solution, according to Xing et al. (82). They claimed that the creation of collagen protein-based hydrogels was caused by electrostatic interaction between anionic clusters ((AuCl₄)) and positively charged collagen chains. Meanwhile, the inclusion of gold nanoparticles (GNPs) as cross-linkers boosted the mechanical strength of the structure, owing to the production of GNPs by chemical reduction of anionic clusters. The weak connections between collagen chains and GNPs also encouraged the self-healing and shear-thinning properties. To decrease tumor development in MCF-7 tumor-bearing mice, they employed collagen-based materials containing both GNPs and meso-tetra-(N-methyl-4-pyridyl) porphine tetrachloride (TMPyP) (photosensitizer) as IHs for combined photothermal treatment (PTT) and photodynamic therapy (PDT). TMPyP gave the resulting hydrogel PDT capabilities and displayed a 120-hour sustained release following tumor injection. GNPs with high photothermal conversion efficiency, on the other hand, may absorb light and convert it to heat, giving the resulting hydrogel PTT capability. Because free TMPyP has a high clearance rate after injection, this IH might improve its bioavailability, which is a big plus. The mice that received 5 times laser irradiation (635 nm, 169.85 mW cm², and 10 min) were well treated, and after 23 days, hematoxylin and eosin (H & E) staining of tumor sections indicated no cancer cells in the region of the original tumor. (82) Using the chemo-photodynamic method, Xu et al. (83) created an in situ forming degradable HA hydrogel for combination cancer treatment. This IH included a photosensitizer, protoporphyrin IX (PpIX), which gave the hydrogel PDT capability, as well as doxorubicin (DOX), a chemotherapeutic drug used in chemo-photodynamic combination treatment to fight cancer. PpIX was chemically attached to adipic dihydrazide modified HA (HA-ADH) to generate HA-ADH-PpIX conjugate, which was used to make hydrogel precursors. As a tiny crosslinker, dialdehyde functionalized thioketal (TKCHO) was produced, along with a ROS-cleavable thioketal linker (TK). The hydrogel (HPTG) was then formed when the precursor solution was injected into the tumor site, thanks to the creation of dynamic covalent acylhydrazone between crosslinker and HA-ADH-PpIX. NIR light irradiation resulted in a large amount of ROS generation in their investigation. The ROS not only enhance the PDT impact, but they also set in motion a series of processes that include cleavage of the ROS-cleavable small molecule crosslinker, IH

degradation, and the consequent release of DOX molecules for cascaded treatment. Light irradiation might be used to control medication release. The biocompatibility of the pH-responsive IH was studied further, with MCF-7, 4T1 cells, and NIH-3T3 cells remaining over 95% following incubation with IHs without light irradiation, indicating great biocompatibility and excellent safety. The viability of MCF-7 cells was reduced in a time-dependent irradiation manner when exposed to LED light (633nm, 20 mW cm²), confirming the formulation's PDT effectiveness. The results showed that the suggested IH could keep the PpIX agent in vivo for a longer duration and that it could lessen the PpIX's excessive aggregation and quenching effects. After 18 days, DOX-loaded HPTG had the highest inhibition effect on tumor growth (tumor volume and tumor weight) compared to other groups, including free DOX, HPTG with and without laser irradiation, DOX-loaded HPTG without laser irradiation, and control group (saline) with and without laser irradiation, due to the combined effect of PDT and chemotherapy. H & E staining confirmed that a combination of DOX-loaded HPTG and laser treatment totally suppressed the development of 4T1 tumors. (83) In situ, generating HPTG in vivo also showed a time-dependent biodegradation pattern (disappearance 35 days after injection), which was attributable to the polysaccharide HA's superior biodegradability.

Multi-responsive silk fibroin (SF) IHs were created by Gou et al. (84) to trigger chemo/PTT/PDT therapy at the same time. The hydrophilic SF (HSF) isolated from regenerated SF (RSF) was used in this work to self-assemble into a hydrogel via the creation of sheet structures and hydrogen-bonding interactions. Furthermore, Cy7, a near-infrared (NIR) irradiation absorbing dye with photothermal conversion potential, was used as the photosensitizer in this triple-therapy technique. In addition, the anticancer medication DOX was encapsulated with Cy7 in the HSF-based IH that was produced. HSF provided shear-thinning, injectability, and self-healing characteristics to the hydrogel by forming-sheet structures. Unlike the RSF solution, the HSF solution gelled in 6 hours at 37 degrees Celsius. The freeze-dried samples' SEM pictures revealed evident cyclic morphological alterations between densely coupled mesoscale multilayer structures and loosely linked multilayer structures, which were caused by shear-thinning stress and subsequent self-healing during the resting period. DOX/Cy7 loading had no effect on gelation. The photothermal ability of Cy7 was not reduced after hydrogel formation, and after 10 minutes of NIR irradiation, the temperature of Cy7 solution and Cy7-hydrogel increased to 55 and 56 °C, respectively, which is significantly higher than the minimum threshold temperature for tumor ablation (43 °C). In vitro drug release experiments revealed that the HSF-based IH was sensitive to pH (higher release at low pH), H₂O₂, and glutathione, with acidity and H₂O₂ efficiently accelerating the DOX release rate from HSF, reaching an ultimate release of 90% in the presence of H₂O₂ (1 mm) at pH 6 and after a 6-day incubation period. At 10 minutes, 48 hours, and 98 hours following NIR irradiation, the thermal infrared camera revealed a dramatically raised temperature of tumors treated with both Cy7 solution and Cy7-hydrogel compared to the PBS group as a negative control. It was discovered that irradiating the IH with NIR light at a wavelength of 808 nm dramatically increased DOX release, confirming the IH's light-responsive activity. Finally, when compared to single-modal therapies, in vivo antitumor studies over 20 days demonstrated that the DOX/Cy7-hydrogel exhibited the highest inhibition rate and therapeutic effectiveness against cancer under NIR irradiation. (84)

According to Jiang et al., nanoparticles have also been used to make hydrogels. (86) Palladium (Pd) nanosheets were combined with thiol-terminated four-arm polyethylene glycol (4arm-PEG-thiol) in their study, with the Pd nanosheets acting as the crosslinker and an IH obtained thanks to the creation of dynamic PdS bonds between the Pd nanosheets and the

4arm-PEG-thiol. Furthermore, DOX was introduced into the aforementioned hydrogel as an anticancer agent.

Furthermore, the Pd nanosheets within the IH structure could rapidly absorb the irradiated NIR and convert it to heat due to their high photothermal conversion efficiency. Through activation of the PTT action of Pd NSs and promotion of DOX release from the hydrogel, NIR laser irradiation provided a synergistic chemo-photothermal therapy to attack cancer. IH may prevent nanoparticles from aggregating and improving their stability, while stopping them from diffusing out of IH may lessen their potential toxicity. The live/dead cell labeling using 4T1 cells revealed the Pd cross-linked IH's good combinatorial performance in cancer treatment via regulated DOX release and hyperthermia. As a result, the performance of this IH was assessed in vivo in 4T1 tumor-bearing mice, and it was discovered that the DOX-loaded IH could be easily injected into solid tumors and that NIR irradiation suppressed tumor development and metastasis. (86) (86) (86) Because most methods for using nanoparticles as crosslinkers necessitate additional surface modification of nanoparticles, this work developed a simple preparation method without surface modification of nanoparticles and used an effective anticancer nanosystem, which can be used in future studies to engineer photothermal and responsive drugs using other 2D nanostructures as a crosslinker. Zhou et al. (87) took use of the HA-based IH's multistage-targeted gold/mesoporous silica core-shell nanocomposites for chemo-photothermal cancer treatment. The core-shell structure of nanoparticles was verified by SEM images. By forming appropriate pores, the core-shell nanoparticles aid in the loading of anticancer medicines. DOX was loaded into gold mesoporous silica nanoparticles (Au@MPP), and subsequently DOX-encapsulated nanoparticles were implanted into the HA-based IH (Au@MPPD@HA) by covalent cross-linking of tyrosine functionalized HA (HA-Tyr) to Au@MPP under HRP catalysis. On the surface of Au@MPP, phenol groups and the mitochondrial targeting function triphenylphosphine were coupled. The HA fragments on these nanoparticles may target the CD44 receptors on the cancer cell surface with precision. The tumor's produced hyaluronidase (HAase) encouraged hydrogel degradation at the tumor location, resulting in the release of Au@MPP nanoparticles and penetration into the deep tumor. Finally, the DOX was preferentially carried into cancer cells and mitochondria by the released nanoparticles. The PTT behavior was generated by the Au nanoparticles, and the resulting hyperthermia increased the release of DOX under NIR irradiation. In vitro investigations revealed that the Au@MPPD@HA was enzyme sensitive, and that DOX release was increased by 60% in the presence of HAase. In the absence of enzyme, however, DOX release was only 7% after two days. After 48 hours, NIR irradiation might increase DOX release by roughly 80%. Furthermore, in vivo experiments on mice with MGC-803 tumors revealed that after Au@MPPD@HA injection and NIR irradiation, the local temperature reached 62 and 75 °C within 5 and 10 minutes, respectively, whereas the temperature in the saline and HA gel treated groups increased to 38 °C, indicating that this system has excellent photothermal conversion capability. When compared to other groups, the DOX-loaded IH coupled with NIR irradiation had the greatest inhibitory impact on tumor development, indicating a synergistic combination of tumor targeting, chemotherapy, and PTT for cancer treatment. After 21 days, the IH's histocompatibility was confirmed. Furthermore, H & E stained sections from tumor tissue demonstrated significant damage and necrotic death of the tumor cells in the DOX-loaded IH group after NIR irradiation, but H & E stained sections from normal organs exhibited no clear adverse effects of this DOX-loaded IH. (87)

Zheng et al., (88) devised and constructed an in situ thermogelling CS IH incorporating MoS₂/Bi₂S₃-PEG (MBP) nanosheets and DOX for colon cancer hyperthermia and chemotherapy. The solution changed from sol to gel at 37 °C due to hydrogen bonding increase, electrostatic attraction, and hydrophobic contact between the CS and-glycerophosphate (-GP). The addition of a photothermal agent capable of absorbing NIR in the range of two biological windows, comprising the first (700–980 nm) and second (1000–1400 nm), might greatly improve the system's PTT capacity. DOX had no effect on the hydrogel's NIR absorption, according to the results. Under NIR irradiation (808 nm, 1W cm²), the tumor surface temperature reached 45.76 and 60.43 °C after 30 s and 5 min, respectively. Furthermore, the NIR light was able to control DOX release by increasing local temperature, and the tumor volume was significantly reduced after 14 days as a result of the photo/chemotherapy combination. Antibacterial studies against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) revealed the antibacterial behavior of the CS-based IH due to inherent bacteriostatic activity of CS with a rate of 40.28 percent, indicating that the suppression of the autoimmune system as a result of cancer and the use of chemotherapy can increase the risk of bacterial infection. (88) This antibacterial combinatorial smart system has promise for treating a variety of malignancies, demonstrating that the right mix of photothermal nanomaterials and an IH can kill tumor cells effectively.

Liu et al. (89) reported on the production of an IH using a host–guest interaction between PEG and-cyclodextrin to improve photothermal performance, retention time, and stability of a thermosensitive photothermal network IH (PNT-gel). The conjugated polymer's backbone was grafted with PEG chains, which successfully converted the irradiation NIR to light to induce photothermal efficiency. Furthermore, in this thermo-sensitive IH with low critical solution transition (LCST), just above physiological temperature, the reversible gel–sol transition might improve drug release in response to NIR light, allowing for on-demand drug release. (90)

The polypeptide and hollow gold nanoshells (HAuNS) were developed by Jin et al. (90) for synergistic chemo-photothermal treatment of the HepG2 malignancy. In their study, positive-charged DOX and negatively-charged polypeptide PC10A were coated layer by layer on the surface of negatively charged HAuNS to create PC10A/DOX/HAuNS IH, with one part of the DOX adsorbed on the HAuNS surface and the other incorporated into the PC10A hydrogel, resulting in sustained drug release. A 0.25 mm needle was easily used to inject PC10A/DOX/HAuNS IH. The photothermal treatment of this non-toxic hydrogel killed the tumor cells, while the DOX release suppressed and removed the remaining tumor cells. (number 90) The intensity of IR783 fluorescence in the control group injected with free IR783 solution swiftly declined on the first day and practically disappeared on day 6. A definite fluorescent signal of IR783 was observed in the PC10A/IR783 hydrogel group until day 30, indicating that IR783 was released continuously from the PC10A/IR783 hydrogel in tumors. Similarly, in the control group, no fluorescence signal of free IR783 was seen in the tumor and main organs except the liver, whereas IR783 in the PC10A hydrogel was primarily seen at the tumor site at day 6 after injection, indicating the potential of PC10A hydrogel as a preeminent drug carrier for long-term chemotherapy without distribution to other organs.

The PC10A polypeptide was also coupled with PTX and Ag₂S quantum dots to deliver chemo/phototherapy against the SKOV3 ovarian cancer tumor in another study. (91) In this study, the PC10A/Ag₂S QD/PTX nanogels were initially synthesized by ultrasonically loading Ag₂S quantum dots (QDs) and PTX into polypeptide PC10A nanogels. After that, the

PC10A/Ag₂S/PTX nanogels were dissolved in the PC10A hydrogel, yielding an IH capable of cancer multi-therapy. IH can extend the residence period of nanogel by localizing it. The non-toxicity of this IH was established in both in vitro and in vivo tests. According to the scientists, the PC10A/Ag₂S/PTX combination could successfully reduce the proliferation of human ovarian cancer cells (SKOV3 cells) and outperformed single NIR photothermal or chemotherapeutic treatments. Fluorescence and photoacoustic (PA) imaging were employed to monitor the in vivo degradation of IH due to the optical characteristics of Ag₂S QDs. The Ag₂S QD fluorescence signal was found for 35 days, demonstrating a long-term breakdown of the hydrogel in vivo. In addition, the PA signal at the tumor location decreased with time (till 9 days), which was consistent with fluorescence imaging. (91)

Other researchers have followed suit, using gold nanostructures and DOX in thermoresponsive IH to give chemo-phototherapy. (92) a He et al. (93) developed a multi-stimulus (pH, enzymes, and near-infrared light)-responsive IH based on amphoteric gelatin nanoparticles (Gela NPs) and polydopamine nanoparticles (PDA NPs) loaded with DOX for combined chemo-photothermal cancer therapy. The hydrogel was supplied with PTT ability thanks to PDA NPs with strong photothermal conversion potential. After DOX was loaded into PDA NPs, the Gela NPs and DOX-PDA NPs were mixed at a basic pH (pH 12), and the system pH was decreased to less than the Gela NPs' isoelectric point, causing charge reversal and the development of a uniform hydrogel. This device might be used as a smart DOX carrier, responding to acidic pH, enzyme, and NIR. The DOX release was enhanced by the acidic pH, which is due to enhanced DOX solubility and the repulsion between positively charged Gela NPs and DOX at acidic pH. The IH was able to release DOX into the tumor location in a continuous and regulated way thanks to the sensitivity of GEL NPs to the acidic pH of the tumor microenvironment and PDA NPs to NIR laser irradiation. (93) Other researchers have also attempted to use other IH structures in conjunction with photothermal agents and anticancer medicines, as well as X-ray radiation. (94) Magnetic hyperthermia, in addition to NIR-triggered hyperthermia, is another mechanism that can be exploited for combination cancer treatment. Zhang and Song (95) developed a new cancer multi-therapy system using superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) and the tumor necrosis factor-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL). Through electrical and hydrophobic interaction between positively charged TRAIL and oleic acid-coated SPIONs and negatively charged poly (organophosphazene), they produced injectable, biodegradable, and thermosensitive TRAIL/SPION noncomplex hydrogels (T/S-NHs) for this purpose (PPZ). At body temperature (37 °C), this thermosensitive IH converted to hydrogel, and T/S noncomplex release was enhanced under magnetic hyperthermia (43 °C). (95)

Imaging-guided tumor ablation is another development in cancer multitherapy. Zhao et al. (96) devised and developed a phase-changeable alginate-based IH for chemotherapy and synergistic hyperthermia. They created an alginate/MoS₂/Bi₂S₃-poly (ethylene glycol) (MBP)/DOX (AMD) hydrogel by encapsulating DOX and MBP nanosheets in an alginate/MoS₂/Bi₂S₃-poly (ethylene glycol) (MBP)/DOX (AMD) hydrogel via binding between-L-guluronic blocks of alginate and calcium ions. Furthermore, in vivo tests showed that MBP nanosheets and DOX may offer computed tomography/PA imaging-guided tumor cell targeting via photothermal and chemotherapeutic processes, respectively. The photothermal conversion efficiency of this alginate-based IH was 42.7 percent, and the drug diffusion from the IH was enhanced after photothermal transformation of the MBP nanosheets. More intriguingly, the encapsulated MBP and DOX might be retained by this unique IH structure, preventing their release into the circulation. (96)

Another way to treat numerous cancers is to combine irradiation and chemotherapy, which allows radioactive agents and anticancer medications to be put onto the IH at the same time. Puente et al. (97) used this technique to target glioblastoma (GBM) in the brain, which is completely diverse. They created a CS-based IH that could release temozolomide (TMZ) as a chemotherapeutic agent in a controlled manner while simultaneously retaining iodine as a radioactive isotope inside its network. The iodine isotopes might be kept for more than 42 days, according to the *in vitro* studies. The TMZ, on the other hand, was totally provided on-demand within 48 hours. Injectable chemo-radio-hydrogel implants, according to this study, might be useful tools for improving GBM local chemoradiotherapy. (97)

Immunotherapy can be used in conjunction with photothermal cancer treatment using IHs, in addition to research into cancer cell targeting. Mei et al. (98) loaded the photothermal medicine methylene blue and the immunological agent imiquimod (R837) into a collagen/alginate IH with shear-thinning characteristic that was made by co-assembly of positively charged collagen and negatively charged alginate. The researchers discovered that PTT triggered tumor-associated antigens (TAA)-related immune responses after intratumoral injection of the collagen/alginate hydrogel. TAA and R837, generated by IH, were combined to generate a vaccination that successfully reduced cancer metastasis by activating an antitumor immune response. (98)

4 IHs for Wound Healing that are Multi-Therapeutic

The design and manufacturing of a 3D structure to control re-epithelialization and dermal regeneration of cutaneous wounds and epithelial tissues has long been a key focus of biomaterial-related research. (99) Several therapeutic compounds, as well as delivery technologies, are being developed to treat difficult-to-heal lesions. We'll go through several instances of nano-engineered IHs for combined wound treatment in this section. In comparison to monotherapy, IHs can be used to administer antibacterial medicines and growth factors concurrently to the wound site, resulting in improved treatment of chronic wounds that are predisposed to infection.

For example, Qu et al. (100) synthesized N-carboxyethyl chitosan (CEC) and oxidized HA to create a multifunctional IH for wound healing (OHA). An aniline tetramer was grafted onto the OHA (OHA-AT). The OHA-AT/CEC was then synthesized by dissolving the CEC polymer in PBS solution and then adding OHA-AT. The hydrogel was made by combining the CEC and OHA-AT solutions and forming a Schiff base link between their functional groups at 37 °C. During the synthesis process, medicines like amoxicillin were used to load medicines into the produced IHs. The AT was discovered to improve mechanical characteristics and lengthen the gelation time. Through a diffusion mechanism, these IHs were able to release up to 73 percent amoxicillin after 48 hours, resulting in considerable antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *E. coli*. Surprisingly, the HCl-doped OHA-In/CEC hydrogels were successful at scavenging ROS, as seen by the decrease of, -diphenyl—picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radicals, which were scavenged at about 80% in an AT concentration-dependent manner. Higher AT content in the structure of IHs resulted in quicker wound healing than gels with lower AT content, which can be related to AT's antioxidant activity, which transfers electrons to free radicals. IH was also shown to have anti-inflammatory, conductivity, and angiogenesis effects. Furthermore, this IH had a substantially quicker wound healing rate than commercial counterparts, resulting in a larger density of fibroblasts and improved collagen deposition and vascular regeneration. (a hundred) Diabetic wounds are challenging to maintain because of their high vulnerability to

microbial infection due to vascular dysfunction. Chen et al. (101) developed an IH based on the AgS coordination link between multi-arm thiolated polyethylene glycol (SH-PEG) and silver nitrate to address this issue (AgNO_3). Ag^+ 's bacteria-killing effect has been linked to improved diabetic wound healing. The hydrogel was provided with self-healing and injectability qualities as a result of this form of cross-linking. During cross-linking, the angiogenic agent deferoxamine (DFO) was added. In vivo tests revealed that the diabetic skin lesion was effectively repaired, as well as increased angiogenic and antibacterial properties. In addition, in vitro antibacterial activity was assessed by observing the clear zone of inhibition (ZOI) around the hydrogel against *S. aureus*, and in vivo antibacterial activity was assessed by immunofluorescent staining with *S. aureus* antibodies, indicating that DFO loaded hydrogel could effectively inhibit bacterial growth, owing to iron chelation and subsequent amplification of bacterial genes. Increased CD31 expression and a considerable rise in vascular endothelial growth factor expression were used to indicate neovascularization (VEGF). In addition, in the presence of DFO-loaded IH, re-epithelialization and in vivo wound healing abilities were significantly enhanced. Kong et al. (102) inserted DFO and bioactive glass (BG) into the alginate-gluconolactone IHs as angiogenesis stimulators to cure diabetic chronic skin abnormalities in rats. In compared to monotherapy with either BG or DFO, the combination of BG and DFO demonstrated superior effects on migration and tube formation of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs). (102)

Li et al. (103) created a biocompatible IH employing sodium alginate (SA) and the bioactive hardystonite (HS) bioceramic as a multifunctional injectable wound dressing that could inhibit bacterial growth while also promoting angiogenesis and wound healing. Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Si ions were released by HS, with Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions acting as crosslinkers for hydrogel production via double ion cross-linking. In addition, Zn^{2+} ions might provide nourishment for wound repair and function as antimicrobial components, whereas Si ions might promote wound healing by inducing angiogenesis. Controlling the gelation process of the hydrogel was done by modulating the release of the integrated Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions from HS, since the quick interaction between SA and divalent ions is a barrier to injectability. The SA/HS composite hydrogel displayed a 100% antibacterial rate in both extract assay and direct contact assay antibacterial tests, but the pure SA hydrogel failed to produce antibacterial effects. In vitro investigations showed that the IH may promote the proliferation and migration of both HDFs and HUVECs, in addition to antibacterial activities. In vivo tests, on the other hand, revealed considerable epithelial and blood vessel development, indicating that this IH has a broad therapeutic potential. (103)

One of the biggest drawbacks of traditional IHs for co-delivery into the wound site is their lack of self-healing capacity, which leads to external pressures damaging them during clinical therapy, especially for irregular wound sites. (104) Damage to IHs during wound care might result in loss of function and a higher risk of bacterial infection at the wound site. Chen et al. (105) used an interaction of aminated gelatin (NGel), oxidized dextran (ODex), and adipic acid dihydrazide to construct a covalent dynamic IH with the capabilities of self-healing, antibacterial property, and continual drug release to address these issues (ADH). The imine and acylhydrazone connections are thought to be responsible for IH's self-healing abilities. The IHs were made with basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF)@poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) microspheres and chlorhexidine acetate (CHA). After swelling, the designed hydrogel maintained its morphological integrity and had high biodegradability. They found that the modified IH might enhance cell proliferation and wound healing by releasing bFGF over time and releasing CHA in bursts. (105)

Because of their similarities to ECM, IHs can be employed for co-delivery of cells and therapies in addition to drug molecules. (106) For example, Zhao et al. (107) used benzaldehyde-capped PEG (OHC-PEG-CHO), phenylboronic-modified chitosan (CSPBA), and poly (vinyl alcohol) to build pH-and glucose-sensitive IHs by covalent crosslinking of imine bond and phenylboronate ester (PVA). During the in situ crosslinking, fibroblasts and insulin were loaded into the IHs. The system was able to release required components for wound healing at moderately acidic pH due to the stability of the imine bond at physiological pH and its instability at acidic pH. The diol moieties of glucose bind strongly to boronic acid derivatives in these modified IHs, forming a reversible boronate ester. The addition of imine bonds (benzoicimine bonds) and phenyl boronic acid moieties to the altered IHs resulted in dual responsive insulin and fibroblast release at the wound site in a streptozotocin-induced diabetic rat model, according to the researchers.

Collagen deposition, neovascularization, and the healing process of diabetic wounds were all improved by the insulin/cell-loaded IHs. Poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) –gelatin hydrogel was also used by Dong et al. (62) to promote cutaneous wound healing and stem cell retention. The hydrogel was made by combining the acrylate groups of poly (ethylene glycol) diacrylate (polyPEGDA) polymers with thiolated anions from thiolated gelatin in a Michael-type addition process (Gel-SH). In a brief time of 2 minutes, gelation was generated in response to physiological circumstances. Murine adipose-derived stem cells (ASCs) were encapsulated into the IH in this study. The hydrogel was able to sustain cell survival, proliferation, migration, and retention better than direct cell distribution to the wound site due to its 3D network structure and structural resemblance to ECM. When comparing the "hydrogel+cells" group to the "cells alone" group, bioluminescence imaging revealed that the "hydrogel+cells" group produced considerably stronger bioluminescence signal in vivo for up to 14 days. The hydrogel also has changeable mechanical properties, biodegradability, and biocompatibility, all of which allow it to be used for cell engraftment. The cell loaded IH dramatically reduced the quantity of macrophages, which was linked to the efficient role of IH in wound healing, according to CD68 immunohistochemical labeling. Additionally, CD31 immunohistochemistry staining revealed that combining cells and IH might improve angiogenesis. Finally, wound closure was substantially quicker in the hydrogel+cells group than in the other groups. (62)

5 Treatments for Tissue Regeneration Caused by IH

Insufficient cell motility, loss of cell viability following single-cell suspension injections, stress responses of cells into 2D constructs, and activation of inflammatory responses are still issues with tissue engineering procedures due to the sluggish biodegradation rate of scaffolds.(108) Furthermore, their therapeutic applications have been hampered by expensive costs, time-consuming methods, and poor bio-mimicking. (110) Long-term tissue remodeling by IHs, on the other hand, provides a suitable substrate for encapsulating many types of pharmacological molecules or cells without losing their bioactivity for multi-therapy reasons. (111) In fact, combining tissue similarity with medication delivery is a viable strategy for treating tissue damage caused by IHs. (112)

5.1 Tissue Engineering of Cartilage

Different therapeutic chemicals and cell types can be fed into the IHs to induce cartilage tissue regeneration in a synchronized manner. To promote articular cartilage regeneration, Sá-Lima et al. (113) produced stimuli-responsive chitosan-starch IHs coupled with encapsulated adipose-derived stromal cells. The addition of starch to the IHs enhanced the degradation

profile and encouraged chondrogenic differentiation of adipose-derived stromal cells for cartilage regeneration, according to the scientists. (113) In another study, chondrocytes and poly (N-isopropylacrylamide)-co-acrylic acid IH containing transforming growth factor 3 (TGF3) were employed to generate neocartilage. When compared to control IHs, the modified IHs demonstrated more chondrogenic differentiation eight weeks after injection. (114)

Arora et al. (115) have demonstrated that articular cartilage abnormalities may be treated with a mix of cells, growth factors, and biomaterial scaffolds. They created an IH using carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), sulfated carboxymethyl cellulose (sCMC), and gelatin that was crosslinked in situ using HRP enzyme to transfer TGF-1, fat pad derived MSCs, and articular chondrocytes (ACs) to a cartilage defect location to stimulate TGF-1 mediated chondrogenesis. When compared to control hydrogels, TGF-loaded hydrogels resulted in greater cell survival, greater sulfated glycosaminoglycans (sGAGs), and collagen deposition. Furthermore, adding TGF-1 to the hydrogels boosted hyaline cartilage marker expression and deposition while decreasing fibrocartilage and hypertrophic marker deposition. The scientists found that cellulose-based hydrogels can be used to offer cartilage tissue engineering materials at a low cost. (115)

5.2 Cardiac Tissue Engineering

Despite the fact that multiple research groups have proven that traditional tissue engineering procedures (direct injection of multiple cell types into the heart tissue) might enhance cardiac function after a myocardial infarction (MI), cell survival after transplantation has been shown to be poor. (116) The combination of cell therapy and in situ tissue engineering can be considered an ideal solution for protecting the cell-graft from inflammation in the ischemic environment of an infarction and resulting in better functional outcomes than injecting human embryonic stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes directly into the infarcted region. (117) In a chronic heart failure model in rats, Song et al. (118) produced acrylated HA IHs incorporating stem cell homing factor (SDF-1) and angiogenic peptides (Ac-SDKP) to stimulate the recruitment of stem cells to the site of damage while also increasing the expression of angiogenic genes. It was discovered that IHs having just SDF-1 or Ac-SDKP failed to promote cardiac regeneration, but IHs having both factors improved mature vessel development and improved cardiac function. (118)

Despite these advancements, there are still several drawbacks to cell-based treatment for MI, such as low cell transport efficiency, limited cell retention in the site of damage, and poor survival of retained cells in a ROS-rich milieu. In a rat model of MI, Hao et al. (119) used IHs made by a moderate gelation procedure and ionic cross-linking between alginate and divalent cations (Ca^{2+}) in the presence of fullereneol nanoparticles to transfer stem cells to the site of damage. In the presence of fullereneol nanoparticles, the hydrogel was made utilizing a moderate gelation method and ionic cross-linking between alginate and divalent cations (Ca^{2+}). The hydrogel's antioxidant activity is enhanced by the addition of fullereneol nanoparticles, which trap ROS free radicals. In addition, the hydrogel may provide structural support to the left ventricle. This hydrogel demonstrated minimal toxicity and decreased oxidative stress in brown adipose derived stem cells (BADSCs). Through activation of the extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) and p38 pathways, as well as inhibition of the c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) pathway, it stimulated angiogenesis and led to increased survival, cardiomyogenic differentiation, and proliferation of BADSCs even in the presence of ROS. (119)

Injectable hydrogels for cardiac regeneration have significant limitations in terms of self-healing and conductivity.(120) These flaws cause hydrogels to be damaged by external pressures and prevent them from being used for a long time with a stable function for cell healing. In fact, due to the heart's contraction characteristic, the cell delivery vehicles must withstand a significant mechanical force upon injection, which raises the danger of IH injury. (121) The use of conductive polymers in self-healing IHs can aid in the proliferation and differentiation of electrically sensitive cells, including cardiac and myoblast cells. (14, 122) If you're looking for a unique way to express yourself, Dong et al. (123) used the dynamic covalent Schiff base reaction between benzaldehyde moieties of dibenzaldehyde-terminated PEG and amine moieties of chitosan-graft-aniline tetramer to make conductive IHs with self-healing properties. The conductivity of IHs was observed to be remarkably similar to that of native myocardium (ranging from 2.29 10³ to 2.42 10³ S cm⁻¹), which the authors ascribed to the presence of aniline tetramer in the structure of IHs. This IH demonstrated outstanding cell transportation carrier characteristics that supported cell survival. (123)

5.3 Bone-Associated Defects Tissue Engineering

Poor angiogenesis inside tissue-engineered grafts is one of the key drawbacks of bone tissue engineering, which may restrict its clinical use for the healing of extensive bone lesions.(124) Oliviera et al. (125) assessed the possibility of electrospun poly (lactic acid) (PLA) fiber-based membranes incorporating calcium phosphate (CaP) ormoglass particles to enhance angiogenesis to overcome this limitation. By distributing the CaP ormoglasses inside a (hydroxypropyl) methylcellulose (HPMC) matrix, an IH containing CaP ormoglasses was created. This composite has the ability to regulate calcium release in a steady and sustained way, which results in the interior section of the bone tissue mending at a slower and longer rate. The production of calcium ions by bone marrow progenitor cells, as well as the continued production of proangiogenic cytokines, contributed to rapid bone growth and angiogenesis. However, for IHs to regenerate bone properly, a formulation with desired self-healing and antimicrobial capabilities is required. To meet these needs, bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP-2) laden adhesive liposomes (A-LIP) were mixed into PEG hydrogel to create adhesive lipo-hydrogel (A-LIP-PEG). In the presence of A-LIP, coordination cross-linking between thiolated PEG (SH-PEG) and Ag produced the hydrogel. The hydrogel's self-healing and injectability were enhanced by the coordination cross-linking between SH-PEG and Ag. Furthermore, the addition of Ag in the formulation resulted in antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. A-LIP was released from the hydrogel and attached to the tissue after injection of the formulation into the target region, resulting in a long-lasting and effective local drug depot. In comparison to typical lipo-hydrogels, A-LIP-PEG with tissue adhesion ability demonstrated greater in vitro osteogenic differentiation and better bone restoration (LIP-PEG). As a result, after 14 and 21 days of incubation in osteoblastic induction media, the A-LIP-PEG group had more calcium nodules than the LIP-PEG and control groups. This technique showed promise in repairing a localized bone cavity that had been injured. (126)

The A-LIP released by A-LIPPEG, on the other hand, significantly increased the relative fluorescence intensity (100 20%) as an indicator of osteocalcin (OCN) expression (green), whereas the LIP-PEG and control groups had significantly lower fluorescence intensity (46 8% and 4%, respectively), indicating that A-LIPPEG has a high potential for enhancing BMSC osteogenic differentiation. Micro-CT scans of bone healing revealed that the A-LIP-PEG treatment group had significantly more mineralization and fracture repair than the control and LIP-PEG groups.

Kocak et al. (21) created pH-and temperature-sensitive IHs based on CS and hydroxyapatite (HA) composite materials loaded with heparin (Hep) to promote angiogenesis toward bone repair and regeneration. Using the sol-gel method, hydrogel precursor solutions with varying concentrations of Hep were produced. By injecting injectable solutions onto the ex-ovo chick chorioallantoic membrane (CAM), the researchers were able to assess angiogenesis. Inducing microvasculature in the CAM test was validated by histological analysis. Similarly, using lower quantities of Hep in the IHs increased the effectiveness of the pro-angiogenic response. Before and after sample implantation, the total survival rates of CAM trials were 45–50 percent and 70–80 percent, respectively. (21) a

Because rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a disease with complicated pathogenicity, treatment systems should function through several mechanisms centered on anti-inflammation and osteogenesis. Traditional approaches have side effects and are confined to one or two mechanisms while ignoring the others. Pan et al. (127) investigated a novel platform for RA therapy that included black phosphorus nanosheets (BPNs) with platelet-rich plasma (PRP)-CS thermoresponsive IH. Under NIR irradiation, BPNs with high photothermal conversion efficiency and ROS production might be used to eliminate hyperplastic synovial tissues. Furthermore, PRP might aid in the adhesion and proliferation of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), as well as the mechanical and biodegradability of the CS hydrogel. In addition to lubrication and cartilage preservation, CS thermosensitive hydrogel with outstanding rheological properties might regulate drug release through thermosensitivity and biodegradability. Furthermore, the breakdown products of BPNs could be transformed in situ into P-based agents, which improve the osteogenesis process by calcium-extracted biomineralization by the in situ phosphorus-driven BPNs. Both in vitro and in vivo tests showed that the BPNs/CS/PRP thermoresponsive hydrogel has high promise for treating RA, and the hydrogel's multimodal mode of action paved the road for healing this complicated illness. (127)

In another study, Parameswaran-Thankam et al. (128) used the graft polymerization method to create an injectable thermoresponsive hydroxypropyl guar-graft-poly (N-vinyl caprolactam) (HPG-g-PNVCL) copolymer, which was then modified with nano-hydroxyapatite (n-HA) by in situ covalent cross-linking using the divinyl sulfone (The plant-derived polymer hydroxypropyl guar gum was utilized to increase the bioactivity of poly (N-vinyl caprolactam) and prevent the beginning of an acute inflammatory response. The researchers put ciprofloxacin, a popular antibiotic, into the composite to boost antibacterial activity. In vitro tests demonstrated that the hydrogel may release medication molecules over an extended period of time. In vitro biomineralization studies using simulated body fluid (SBF) for 14 days revealed that apatite-like structure was deposited on the surface of the HPG-g-PNVCL/n-HA/DVS scaffold, which was confirmed by SEM, and the Ca/P ratio increased from 0.83 to 2.00 within 7 days, which is similar to the human body. As a result, this system was extremely successful for tissue regeneration due to its calcium-rich apatite-forming capabilities, high bioactivity, and efficient promotion of osteoblast cell differentiation. (128)

5.4 Tissue Engineering in Dentistry

Periodontal disease, tooth lesion, and tooth loss all have a significant impact on masticatory efficiency and face attractiveness. Combination treatment with injectable biomaterials is an effective way to speed up dental regeneration. (129) Xu et al. (130) created a thermosensitive IH based on CS, b-sodium glycerophosphate (b-GP), and gelatin to promote periodontal

regeneration by regulated release of erythropoietin (EPO) and aspirin. In vitro and in vivo, IHs released aspirin and EPO continuously for at least 21 days without causing harm. Through down-regulation of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) proteins, CS/b-GP/gelatin IHs were able to stop the inflammation and restore the height of the alveolar bone, according to micro-CT and immunohistochemical staining. (130) Tan et al. (131) created a biocompatible supramolecular hydrogel of SDF-1/BMP-2/NapFFY for periodontal tissue regeneration by co-assembling the hydrogelator NapFFY with BMP-2 and SDF-1. Hydrogels were shown to be injectable and capable of filling irregular periodontal bone lesions due to their low G' and G'' values (about 1–30 Pa). They discovered that a hydrogel containing SDF-1 and BMP-2 was filled in the tissue defect area, and that sustained release of periodontal tissue reconstruction stimulators (SDF-1 and BMP-2) resulted in the commencement of the periodontal bone regeneration process. (131) However, due to the intricate anatomy of the root canal system and the short apical access, poor revascularization ability, particularly in endodontic regenerative treatments, is a major barrier in the field of tissue engineering. Silva et al. used injectable and viscoelastic HA-based hydrogels for releasing chemotactic and angiogenic growth factors in research (GFs).

The cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) and platelet lysate were added to HA hydrogels (PL). The CNC gave the HA hydrogel mechanical strength and resistance to enzymatic breakdown. PL also generated chemotactic and proangiogenic growth factors (platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), VEGF). These IHs allow for the release of chemotactic and pro-angiogenic GFs in a regulated manner (PDGF and VEGF). The hydrogel enhanced the vitality of the encapsulated human dental pulp cells due to the PL content (hDPCs). In an in vitro study, the released GFs from the hydrogel attracted dental pulp-origin cells and promoted cell sprouting in an ex vivo study. With its capacity to operate as a GFs controlled delivery system as well as a supporting matrix for cell culture, recruitment, and revascularization induction, this technology has a lot of potential for vascularized tissue engineering applications like regenerative dentistry. (132)

5.5 Nerve Tissue Engineering

To treat nerve injury, IHs can be employed as carriers for neural stem cells and growth factors.(133) Zhao et al. (134), for example, created a thermosensitive IH containing nerve growth factor (NGF) and heparin-poloxamer (HP) for SCI regeneration. They initially synthesized HP using the EDC/NHS approach, and then used the cold approach to make NGF–HP in situ hydrogels. The bioactivity of NGF–HP hydrogels was excellent. In vivo studies in a rat model of SCI revealed that NGF–HP hydrogels improved neuron functioning and tissue shape, as well as inhibited the development of glial scars, more than the free HP hydrogel and NGF therapy groups. The synergistic benefits of NGF–HP hydrogels on SCI regeneration might be explained by NGF's neuroprotective properties and heparin's anti-inflammatory properties. (134) In 2017, the same research used a cold technique to develop GDNF-HP hydrogels and discovered that injecting them into the lesion epicenter after SCI had larger impacts on neural stem cell proliferation and axonal regeneration than free HP hydrogel and GDNF treatment groups. (135, 135) In diabetic rats, Li et al. (136) loaded bFGF and NGF into thermosensitive HP hydrogels for peripheral nerve regeneration. Large amounts of growth factors (GFs) may be loaded into the HP hydrogels and released in a controlled way. Injection of GFs-HP hydrogels into the injury site resulted in greater schwann cell proliferation, axonal regeneration, and remyelination than injection of HP hydrogel alone or direct GFs.(136)

IHs can also be used to restore damaged nerves after an ischemic stroke by delivering stem cells and growth factors at the same time. Moshayedi et al. (137) designed a modified HA hydrogel with heparin bound growth factors and MMP degradable motifs to distribute human neural progenitor cells (iPS-NPCs) and growth factors for nerve regeneration following ischemic stroke in a synchronized manner. Growth factors and heparin were combined into the gel precursor solution before an MMP-degradable peptide cross-linker was added. The up-regulation of GFAP and S100b markers by cells encapsulated in the IHs resulted in greater astrocytic differentiation of iPS-NPCs within the stroke cavity, according to the findings. (137)

Other Inhibitory Hormones (IHs) Applications for Combination Therapy

The researchers evaluated IHs' efficacy in the co-delivery of treatments to give numerous treatments, which is one of its intriguing traits and capabilities. Tuladhar et al. (23) focused on co-delivering treatments to the brain, which is a difficult endeavor owing to the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and off-target effects caused by systemic administration. The medications, such as cyclosporine A (CsA) and erythropoietin (EPO), can have negative side effects. However, local administration of these medications may be a potential way to lessen adverse effects. As a result, they created a form of IH to get around the BBB and, for the first time, co-deliver CsA and EPO in a controlled and local manner. To create a modular delivery system, they put the medications into poly (lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA) particles and dispersed them in a hyaluronan and methylcellulose (HAMC) gel. They encased the composite in a polycarbonate shell and sealed it with dental cement to prevent drug leakage into the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and they implanted the composite into the surface of the rat brain four days after injury to decrease tissue damage from intracranial implants. Both medications may diffuse into the sub-cortical neural stem and progenitor cell (NSPC) niche and stay there for roughly 32 days, according to the findings. The CsA was found to increase striatal plasticity, while the EPO was proven to be beneficial in increasing endogenous NSPCs. Furthermore, these results were only possible due to the local and persistent co-delivery of both medications, which improved tissue healing to the point that the lesion volume in the CsA+EPO treated group was considerably reduced at day 46 compared to day 4 ($p < 0.05$). However, in single drug-treated groups, this substantial difference was not seen. The lesion volume decreased by almost 23% in the CsA-treated group, compared to 27% in the EPO-alone group. This problem demonstrated that CsA and EPO had an additive impact and independent mechanisms on stroke lesion since the lesion volume was reduced by 50% in the CsA+EPO treatment group. (23)

In comparison to exogenous (unbound) growth factor administration, sequestering or attaching pro-angiogenic growth factors to nanoparticles and integration into IHs has been shown to generate persistent activation of cell-surface receptors and better efficacy for the treatment of various diseases. (138) To promote brain healing after stroke, Nih et al. (139) produced in situ gelling HA hydrogels for co-delivery of nanoparticle-clustered VEGF and heparin nanoparticles. When compared to traditional VEGF delivery in the brain, they discovered that heparin nanoparticle-clustered VEGF had stronger effects on normal vascular development, reducing microglia activation, promoting axonal ingrowth, and migration of immature neurons from the subventricular zone to the infarcted region. The anti-inflammatory characteristics of naked heparin particles were found to counteract VEGF's inflammatory action and lead to the establishment of a pro-repair milieu in the infarcted area. (139)

Boffito et al. (140) also formed an IH for the simultaneous administration of copper ions and ibuprofen. To do this, they first created copper-substituted bioactive mesoporous glasses (Cu-MBGs) nano and microparticles, which were then loaded with ibuprofen using the incipient wetness methodology. The amphiphilic polyurethane-based thermosensitive IH was then distributed with this composite. The loaded drug and ions had no effect on the gelation behavior of this IH, as stated. The results showed that this method could deliver Cu²⁺ and ibuprofen in a continuous and coordinated manner, with the released copper ions stimulating the chemical breakdown of polyurethane and controlling the gel residence duration at the pathological site. Overall, this study demonstrated that the IH, in conjunction with MBGs, can be successfully used to create regulated and local co-delivery of therapeutic ions and pharmaceuticals, which is highly desired in the biomedical field.(140)

Fan et al. used Schiff's base reaction to create an IH from natural polysaccharides for medication and cell scaffold co-delivery.(142-143) CMC and oxidized chondroitin sulfate (OCS) were used to cross-link the IH during the manufacturing process, with the mechanism being a reaction between amino and aldehyde groups. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) was placed in the CS-based microspheres and implanted into the CMC-OCS IH for co-delivery. The CS microspheres have the potential to improve the IH's mechanical and bioactive characteristics. Rufaihah et al. (143) used IHs to treat acute MI with GF treatment. They created an IH from polyethylene glycol-fibrinogen (PF), which was used to distribute VEGF and angiopoietin-1 (ANG-1) in a controlled and coordinated manner (PF-VEGF-ANG1), with the goal of increasing myocardial repair and function. In a 30-day period, both VEGF and ANG-1 were released in a controlled manner. As a result of the synergistic actions of VEGF and ANG-1, the cardiac muscle was maintained. In comparison to the saline-treated group and the 1 percent PF-treated group, the 1 percent PF-VEGF-ANG1 group had the highest capillary density in the infarct and peri-infarct areas. Furthermore, the PF-VEGF-ANG-1 hydrogel may function as a mechanical support to help prevent unfavorable cardiac remodeling. Overall, combining treatment with co-delivery of medicines via an IH may help reduce post-MI cardiac dysfunction. (143)

Zhang et al. (144) focused on drug delivery and 3D cell cultivation of L929 cells using an IH, which was synthesized by mixing glycol CS and a dibenzaldehyde terminated copolymer poly (N-isopropyl acrylamide)-co-poly (acrylic acid) (DF poly (NIPAM-co-AA)) solutions, as well as dynamic imine bonds formation between benzaldehyde and amine groups To investigate the use of the produced IH in drug transport, cisplatin, an anticancer agent, and rhodamine B were loaded as drug models in this investigation. According to the scientists, this IH was pH and temperature sensitive and could release the medication in a controlled manner as a function of the surrounding pH and temperature. This non-cytotoxic IH was effectively used for 3D cell culture of L929 cells, resulting in excellent viability (i.e., 90%) after 24 hours of incubation with hydrogel, indicating that hydrogel, by providing a 3D environment for cells to grow, is a promising cell carrier choice. This encouraging result might pave the way for IHs to pursue more work in multimodal treatment, such as simultaneous medication delivery and cell treatment. (144)

Pentlavalli et al. (145) used a simple free-radical polymerization of N-isopropyl acrylamide (NIPAAm) on the alginate backbone while employing ammonium persulfate (APS) and N, N, N', N'-tetramethylethylenediamine to create an in situ generating biocompatible IH (TEMED). At an LCST of 32 °C, which is close to normal body temperature, the resulting hydrogel demonstrated thermoresponsive activity. The hydrogel was biocompatible and

biodegradable, and after eight weeks, it had deteriorated by about 70% due to surface degradation, which is ideal for long-term drug administration. In terms of delivery behavior, it was discovered that at pH 7.4 and 37 °C, the big protein molecule BSA was released slower than NaF from the hydrogel due to contact with the polymeric network. Furthermore, the viscosity of alginate might alter the P's mechanical and structural qualities (Alg-g-NIPAAm). This new thermosensitive IH was also utilized in local and sustained co-delivery of human osteosarcoma (MG63) cells and pig bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (pBMSCs) (pBMSCs). The pBMSCs with uniform dispersion were encased within the IH. By incubating in osteogenic and chondrogenic media, the osteogenic and chondrogenic potential of pBMSCs encapsulated in the P (Alg-g-NIPAAm) hydrogel were evaluated, and after a two-week culture period in both osteogenic and chondrogenic conditions, viability was increased from an initial value of 60 percent to more than 80 percent. The histological assessment demonstrated stronger collagen and sGAGs staining for hydrogels incubated under chondrogenic settings compared to osteogenic settings. At the same time, greater mineralization was reported for hydrogel incubated in osteogenic conditions. Furthermore, the hydrogel incubated in chondrogenic conditions had a high DNA content, which was attributed to the proliferative action of TGF-3 in its media.(145)

Linh et al. (146) created an in situ forming IH by in situ enzymatic crosslinking of tyramine-conjugated gelatin and hydroxyl phenyl acetamide CS in the presence of HRP as a catalyst and hydrogen peroxidase as an antioxidant to deliver human adipose-derived stem cells (hADSC) and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) at the same time with the goal of The in vitro experiment and subcutaneous hydrogel implantation in Balb/c nude female mice demonstrated that the hADSC and the hydrogel formulation were compatible. The biocompatible scaffold with a unique branching network and channels might promote cell infiltration and vascularization, according to histological research. (146)

Conclusions

As many therapeutic treatments are used together, they frequently provide higher benefits, counterbalance drawbacks, and improve treatment outcomes when compared to monotherapy. Injectable biomaterials, whether natural or synthetic, can build degradable networks in situ, reducing patient suffering and expenses while also providing new and promising options for minimally invasive surgery. Biomaterials' capacity to develop and fabricate injectable systems is heavily influenced by their physicochemical and mechanical qualities (147-274).

The design and fabrication of injectable systems containing cells, therapeutic molecules, particles, and biomolecules that can be injected into geometrically complex regions of the body tissues pose a significant challenge because they must ensure drug/biomolecule/material bioactivity as well as cell survival and retention. Hydrogels are a good alternative in this scenario because of their tremendous capacity for manipulation, encapsulation, and co-delivery of medicinal compounds, cells, biomolecules, and nanomaterials. Hydrogels have the benefit of being able to tailor their mechanical and degrading characteristics by modifying the cross-linking process and chemical composition. The capacity to alter the mechanical strength of IHs allows for the in situ co-encapsulation of medicinal chemicals, cells, nanomaterials, and growth factors into the matrix, allowing for multimodal synergistic treatments.

To improve the chances of IHs being translated into the normal clinic, several hurdles and unresolved scientific difficulties must be resolved in the future. To begin, future studies including the use of IHs in multimodal synergistic therapy should be conducted in big animal

models such as monkeys and dogs, or even ex vivo human tissue models. Furthermore, the duration of in vivo evaluations should be extended from weeks to months in order to get reliable and exact data that can be transferred into clinical trials. On the one hand, the next point to consider is the toxicity of certain of the crosslinking agents used in IH production, and therefore the residues will produce unwanted in vivo reactions. Toxic crosslinkers, on the other hand, may interact with therapeutic molecules/biomolecules or nanomaterials trapped in the matrix of hydrogels, causing their bioactivity to be lost. Similarly, the sol–gel transition of IHs is a critical subject that requires a lot of study. A rapid sol–gel transition of the precursor solutions may cause the fluid to become trapped in the needle, whereas high viscosity precursor solutions necessitate high injection force, resulting in hand fatigue for physicians and inconvenience for patients. Other considerations for clinical translation of IHs include rapid drug release and degradation rate. The pace of degradation is crucial in regulating the release of therapeutic substances and tissue regeneration. Fast hydrogel breakdown may cause an initial inflammatory response owing to breakdown products, whereas delayed degradation may result in inadequate therapeutic drug release. As a result, altering the composition, structure, and crystallinity of polymers must be used to tailor the breakdown rate. Expert researchers will be better able to handle these issues if they have a better grasp of the physiochemical characteristics of polymers. Overall, future IH design should place a greater emphasis on constructing simple and well-defined 3D networks with low toxicity, a high biodegradation rate, and adequate functioning.

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